

ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISM FOR SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IN UKRAINE IN THE CONTEXT OF THE TRANSFORMATION OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

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Abstract. Assessment and implementation of the organizational and economic mechanism for sustainable business development in Ukraine in the context of the transformation of the national economy is to ensure balanced development of all sectors of its economy based on the balanced use of resources to solve economic, social and environmental problems. Particular attention should be paid to studying the role of innovation, the management component, the effective operation of all enterprises in the territory, as well as the application of social guarantees and benefits to improve the quality of life of the population.

Keywords domestic business, environmental risks, economic efficiency, innovation, innovative development, sustainable development, principles of sustainable development, national economy, organizational and economic mechanism, resources, social responsibility, sustainability.

Introduction

Research, assessment and forecasting of the effectiveness of the organizational and economic mechanism for sustainable business development in Ukraine in the context of the transformation of the national economy within a regional framework was formed on the basis of materials from the Kyiv region (Performance indicators of economic entities). The level of profitability of agricultural, forestry and fishery enterprises in the Kyiv region over the last decade was determined (Table 1).

Table 1
Dynamics of the level of profitability of agricultural, forestry and fishery enterprises of Kyiv region, 2014-2023.

Years	Profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries, %
2014	5,70
2015	33,55
2016	35,35
2017	11,75
2018	23,85
2019	9,85
2020	15,90
2021	37,24
2022	16,56
2023	13,10

Source: based on Performance indicators of economic entities.

It should be emphasized that the business entities of the Kyiv region occupy 7th place in the rating in 2023 in terms of the level of agricultural, forestry and fishery enterprises, which is an optimistic situation, taking into account all external and internal factors of influence. Next, using economic and mathematical methods and models, we will calculate, analyze, compare, simulate, forecast, and graphically present the level of profitability of the agricultural, forestry and fishery industries of the Kyiv region for the last and future periods.

Five production regressions were selected as statistical data processing tools: linear production regression, logarithmic production regression, power production regression, exponential production regression, and polynomial production regression.

The aim of the article is assessment of the effectiveness of the organizational and economic mechanism for sustainable business development in Ukraine in the context of the transformation of the national economy

Literature review Paying tribute to the significant achievements of scientific research in the field of organizational and economic support for sustainable business development of such Ukrainian scientists as O. M. Alymov, V. D. Bilodid, T. Vlasyuk, V. Geets, M. V. Hnidohy, I. Hryshchenko, L. Hanushchak-Efimenko, I. Hnatenko, V. Gotry, Yu. Danko, M. Zgurovsky, S. M. Ilyashenko, O. Ilyash, A. Oleshko, V. Rossokha, S. Solntseva, V. Tkachuk, M. Shkody, as well as foreign scientists such as A. Atkisson, W. K. Mitchell, B. Santo, B. Twiss, M. Porter, Y. Schumpeter and others, it is worth noting that the organizational and economic tools for sustainable business development in Ukraine require further development, since modern scientific research currently lacks integrity and comprehensiveness in the approach to studying relevant theoretical, methodological and practical issues of forming organizational and economic mechanisms in the context of the transformation of the national economy.

Research methodology To calculate the analytical characteristics of the dynamic series of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries of the Kyiv region, we use Microsoft Excel spreadsheets and the specified trend production models used to study economic processes over time (Kalinichenko, 2021).

According to the results of data processing, linear and nonlinear production regressions of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries of the Kyiv region for the recent period were obtained (Table 2).

Table 2

Linear and nonlinear production regressions of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries in Kyiv region, 2014-2023.

Production regression	Regression equation of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries of Kyiv region	Coefficient of determination, R ²	
Linear production regression	$Y = -0,27x + 21,77$	0,91	

Logarithmic production regression	$Y = 0,61\ln(x) + 19,36$	0,95	the best model by coefficient of determination, R^2
Power production regression	$Y = 13,009x^{0,19}$	0,82	
Exponential production regression	$Y = 15,74e^{0,0172x}$	0,71	
Polynomial production regression	$Y = -0,29x^2 + 2,95x + 15,32$	0,74	

Source: based on Performance indicators of economic entities; Kalinichenko, 2021.

According to the results of processing statistical data of the Kyiv region, we note that the selected production regressions are qualitative and adequate, as evidenced by the coefficient of determination, the sign of which is the approach to 1, the closer the better the model and in the future, this model can be used to forecast economic indicators. The best production nonlinear function of the level of profitability of agriculture, forestry and fisheries of the Kyiv region is logarithmic production regression, the coefficient of determination is 0.95 (Table 2).

The next step is to determine the actual, theoretical and forecast values of the level of profitability of agriculture, forestry and fisheries of the Kyiv region, which are determined by linear and nonlinear production regressions for the last and future periods (Table 3.).

Table 3

Actual, theoretical and forecasted values of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries of Kyiv region determined by linear and nonlinear production regressions, 2014-2023, 2026-2027.

Nº	Years	Level of profitability of agriculture, forestry and fisheries, %	Linear production regression of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries,%	Logarithmic production regression of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries,%	Power production regression of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries,%	Exponential production regression of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries,%	Polynomial production regression of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries,%
1	2014	5,70	21,50	19,97	13,01	16,76	17,98
2	2015	33,55	21,23	20,66	14,84	16,77	20,06
3	2016	35,35	20,96	21,07	16,03	16,79	21,56
4	2017	11,75	20,69	21,36	16,93	16,81	22,48

5	2018	23,85	20,42	21,58	17,66	16,83	22,82
6	2019	9,85	20,15	21,76	18,28	16,85	22,58
7	2020	15,90	19,88	21,92	18,83	16,87	21,76
8	2021	37,24	19,61	22,05	19,31	16,89	20,36
9	2022	16,56	19,34	22,17	19,75	16,91	18,38
10	2023	13,10	19,07	22,27	20,15	16,93	15,82
11	2026		18,80	22,37	20,52	16,95	12,68
12	2027		18,53	22,45	20,86	16,97	8,96
Scenarios			Realistic	Optimistic	Optimistic	Realistic	Pessimistic

Source: based on Performance indicators of economic entities; Kalinichenko, 2021.

From the results of Table 3, we see three scenarios of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries in the Kyiv region determined by linear and nonlinear production regressions: optimistic, realistic and pessimistic.

The most realistic is the level of profitability of agriculture, forestry and fisheries in the Kyiv region determined by linear and exponential production regressions.

Illustratively, the actual and forecast values of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries in the Kyiv region under the realistic scenario, determined by linear and exponential production regressions for the recent and future periods are presented in Fig. 1

Fig. 1. Actual and forecasted values of the profitability level of agriculture, forestry and fisheries of Kyiv region under a realistic scenario, determined by linear and exponential production regressions, 2014-2023, 2026-2027.

Source: based on Performance indicators of economic entities; Kalinichenko, 2021.

Previously, the calculation and analysis of the impact of the main coefficients of innovative activity on the level of profitability of innovative activity of agrarian formations of the Kyiv region was carried out using multiple production functions: power, exponential, exponential and semi-logarithmic. Now we will forecast the level of profitability of innovative activity of agrarian formations of the Kyiv region for the next period. Factor characteristics of the main coefficients of innovative activity were predicted in advance and are used to forecast and assess the effectiveness of the organizational and economic mechanism of sustainable business development. In table. 4, the maximum forecast values of the level of profitability of innovative activity, agrarian formations of the Kyiv region under the influence of the main coefficients of innovative activity using multiple nonlinear functions are formed

Table 4

Maximum forecast values of the level of profitability of innovative activities, agricultural formations of the Kyiv region, 2026-2027.

Using the coefficients of innovation activity of 1 block		
Agricultural enterprise	Indicator Maximum value of the level of profitability of innovative activity, %, 2026 p.	Indicator Maximum value of the level of profitability of innovative activity, %, 2027 p.
FG "Gavryshchuk"	3,14	3,36
FG "Arhat"	2,07	2,10
SG "Coop Agribusiness"	29,83	32,28
STOV "Lyubaretske"	15,90	16,55
TOV "AF Kyivska"	6,26	6,74
FG "TVK"	3,16	3,40
Using the coefficients of innovation activity of block 2		
Agricultural enterprise	Indicator Maximum value of the level of profitability of innovative activity, %, 2026 p.	Indicator Maximum value of the level of profitability of innovative activity, %, 2027 p.
FG "Gavryshchuk"	3,03	3,77
FG "Arhat"	1,80	1,93
SG "Coop Agribusiness"	23,57	23,88
STOV "Lyubaretske"	11,94	12,04
TOV "AF Kyivska"	6,74	6,81
FG "TVK"	2,96	3,03

Source: based on (2, 13-16).

Also, the maximum forecast values of the level of profitability of innovative activity, agrarian formations of the Kyiv region for the next period are summarized for convenience, comparison and the ability to choose the

most influential main coefficients of innovative activity of business entities (Table 5).

Table 4

Maximum forecast values of the level of profitability of innovative activities, agricultural formations of the Kyiv region, 2026-2027.

Agricultural enterprise	block 1		block 2		Comparative characteristics
	Indicator Maximum value of the level of profitability of innovative activity, %, 2026	Indicator Maximum value of the level of profitability of innovative activity, %, 2027	Indicator Maximum value of the level of profitability of innovative activity, %, 2026	Indicator Maximum value of the level of profitability of innovative activity, %, 2027	
FG "Gavryshchuk"	3,14	3,36	3,03	3,77	Forecasting for the long-term period is advisable to be carried out using the coefficients of innovation activity of blocks 1 and 2 Forecasting for the long-term period is advisable to be carried out using the coefficients of innovation activity of block 1
FG "Arhat"	2,07	2,10	1,80	1,93	It is advisable to make forecasts for the long-term period using the coefficients of innovation activity of block 1.
SG "Coop Agribusiness"	29,83	32,28	23,57	23,88	It is advisable to make forecasts for the long-term period using the coefficients of innovation activity of block 1.
STOV "Lyubaretske"	15,90	16,55	11,94	12,04	It is advisable to make forecasts for the long-term period using the coefficients of innovation activity of block 1.
TOV "AF Kyivska"	6,26	6,74	6,74	6,81	It is advisable to make forecasts for the long-term period using the coefficients of innovation activity of blocks 1 and 2.
FG "TVK"	3,16	3,40	2,96	3,03	Прогнозування на довгостроковий період доцільно проводити за коефіцієнтами інноваційної діяльності 1 блоку

Source: based on (2, 13-16).

Conclusions Concluding the assessment of the effectiveness of the organizational and economic mechanism for sustainable business development in Ukraine in the context of the transformation of the national economy, we note that measures to stabilize business entities are not only relevant, but also critically necessary to ensure the stability of the economy as a whole. In the current conditions, when the business environment operates under the pressure of multiple challenges – from military aggression and destruction of infrastructure to inflationary risks and loss of external markets - it is the state policy of sustainable development that should serve as the basis for supporting and restructuring business. The effective functioning of the organizational and economic mechanism requires a comprehensive approach, which includes the creation of favorable institutional conditions, improving the tax and regulatory environment, expanding access to financing, and stimulating the innovative activity of enterprises. It is important that the emphasis of state policy be shifted from short-term "patching crises" to strategically ensuring the stability and competitiveness of national business through the implementation of the principles of sustainable development.

Particular attention should be paid to small and medium-sized enterprises, which, on the one hand, are most vulnerable to external shocks, and on the other hand, are able to demonstrate flexibility, localization and innovation in their activities. Their support should be systemic and focused on developing potential – through training, consultations, preferential lending, as well as promoting participation in public-private partnerships. The formation of mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of sustainable business development is another important area. This is not only about fixing quantitative results (employment levels, tax revenues, production volumes), but also about assessing the social and environmental impact of enterprise activities. Thus, the introduction of a system of key indicators (in particular, according to the ESG methodology) will allow assessing the true contribution of business to the sustainable development of society.

In conclusion, it can be stated that the organizational and economic mechanism of sustainable business development in Ukraine is in the process of formation. Its effectiveness will depend on the ability to harmonize economic, social and environmental goals, adapt the best international practices and create an environment of trust, transparency and partnership. The successful implementation of this approach will ensure not only the recovery of the national economy after crises, but also its sustainable growth in the long term. And the processing of data of business entities by economic and mathematical methods will be able to create a basis for further development, stabilization and avoidance of activity risks. Also, this may provide an opportunity for a promising direction of research and evaluation - the study and assessment of the possibilities of applying foreign experience in optimizing the organizational and economic mechanism of sustainable development of agrarian business in Ukraine, especially medium and small agricultural formations (Vatchenko, Ilchenko, 2011).

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